

The Benefits Derived from the Adoption of Innovations in the Production of Tomatoes in the Gambia

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ABSTRACT:

CONTEXT: This study assessed the adoption of innovations and the production of tomatoes in The Gambia.

OBJECTIVE: The study assessed the benefits derived from the adoption of innovations in the production of tomatoes in The Gambia.

METHODS: A cross-sectional research design was employed for the study. Literature was reviewed in line with the objectives of the study, and the diffusion of innovation theory, innovation transfer was adopted to explain the adoption of innovations in the production of tomatoes. A sample size of 396 was drawn from the population of tomato farmers in two regions using a multi-stage sampling technique. The instruments adopted for data collection were a structured questionnaire, a focus group discussion guide, and a key-informant guide. The data that was collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics, while correlation and linear regression were employed to test the hypothesis at a .05 level of significance

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS: The adopted innovations significantly increased both yield ($p < .001$) and farmer income ($p < .003$). The study, therefore, concludes that there is an association between the adoption of innovations and the production of tomatoes.

SIGNIFICANCE: To improve the production of tomatoes in The Gambia, the study recommended that farmers need access to innovative solutions in weeding, storage, transportation, and marketing. Additionally, establishing robust farmer-to-farmer information networks is essential. Training selected "contact farmers" on agricultural innovations enables them to share knowledge with peers, leading to increased yields and income while reducing postharvest losses.

KEYWORDS: Benefits, Adoption; Innovations; Production; Tomato, The Gambia

INTRODUCTION

Tomato is one of the world's major fresh and processed fruits and is the second most important tomato crop in the world after potatoes (Padmanabhan, Cheema, & Paliyath, 2016; Arah, Ahorbo, Anku, Kumah, & Amaglo, 2016). Tomato belongs to the Solanaceae (nightshade family), genus *Solanum*, species *Lycopersicon*. It is an annual plant that belongs to the family Solanaceae, order Solanales. Tomato plants are mainly cultivated for their edible fruits (Anwar, Fatima, & Mattoo, 2019). It is native to the South American Andes and was introduced to Europe by Spanish people in the sixteenth century, and later it was brought from Europe to South and East Asia, Africa, and the Middle East (Délices et al., 2019; Razifard et al., 2020).

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The tomato is produced along a value chain that encompasses several critical stages that ensure the journey from seed to consumer, including inputs, cultivation (Eze et al., 2019), harvesting (Adebayo et al., 2020), post-harvest handling (Olaoye et al., 2023), processing (Danmaigoro et al., 2024), and marketing (Shukla & Dwivedi, 2020). According to Shukla et al. (2020), this chain is critical for improving farmers' income, reducing post-harvest losses, and ensuring quality for consumers.

Globally, more than 170 nations grow tomatoes (FAO, 2023), with a global production of nearly 189 million tons in 2021. Tomato production rose by around 500% from 1970 to 2022, with Asian output contributing up to 63% of global production and being the primary force behind this astounding surge. China (64.86 MT) is the top producer of tomatoes, sharing nearly 34.72%, followed by India (20.57 MT). Production in Africa increased from 3.49 million metric tons in 1970 to 22.9 million metric tons in 2022, growing at an average annual rate of 4.10%. Egypt was ranked as the largest producer in Africa and 8th in the world (FAO, 2023), and Nigeria was the 2nd largest producer in Africa and ranked 1st in West Africa, while The Gambia's production was estimated at 15,952 metric tons.

According to Trade Data Monitor (2023), tomato consumption globally in 2022/23 was estimated at the 37-million-ton threshold, with North America (USA, Canada, Puerto Rico, etc.) remaining the undisputed world leader, consuming more than a quarter of the annual volume of tomato products, the Australia–New Zealand region in second place (17 kg/person/year), ahead of the Western European Union (15 kg), and non-EU Europe (14.5 kg). The Middle East, Mediterranean Africa, and the Eastern EU rank next, with levels close to 12 kg/person/year. The individual global average remains below 5 kg/year, with Central America, West Africa, and the Far East below this, with levels of between 2 and 4 kg per person per year, and a few regions with very low and difficult-to-specify levels below the 1 kg per person threshold (Trade Data Monitor, 2023).

Tomato production and consumption have increased, and this could be attributed to its importance as it is very beneficial for its healthy vitamins, minerals, carbohydrates, dietary fibers, and essential amino acids, along with iron, phosphorus, and vitamins A and C in sufficient amounts (Rai & Singh, 2022). Vitamin C is important in forming collagen, a protein that gives structure to bones, cartilage, muscle, and blood vessels. It also helps maintain capillaries, bones, and teeth and aids in iron absorption (Luna-Guevara et al., 2014). Tomato fruits are rich in fiber, antioxidants, minor elements (manganese, copper, etc.), and vitamins (B1 and B6), offering therapeutic properties that can treat diarrhoea and hypertension (Ali et al., 2021). Beyond their health benefits, growing tomatoes is a business that brings revenue to growers, agro-dealers, and distributors along the tomato value chain (Goka, Dufrechou, Picouet, & Ameyapoh, 2021). Consequently, much like the tomato industry as a whole, tomato farming presents a genuine possibility to generate a large number of jobs for the populace (Ouattara & Konate, 2024). In order to solve problems with food security, public health, and poverty alleviation in the nation, tomato farming can be a key component (Ouattara & Konate, 2024).

Despite their economic and health benefits to farmers, tomato production is faced with production challenges along the value chain in both developed and developing countries. Globally, some of the challenges faced in tomato production include high cost of inputs, pests and diseases, postharvest losses, marketing, and biotic and abiotic stress, whose expressions and severity vary across the growing climates in the world (Gatahi, 2020; Ogunsola & Ogunsola, 2021). Similar challenges are also highlighted in some literature in Africa: high incidences of fungal diseases and pests, low soil fertility, limited tomato breeding, climate change-induced stresses, lack of adequate inputs due to prohibitive costs, and the failure of smallholder farmers to take advantage of available innovations such as the use of improved seeds (Dube, Ddamulira, & Maphosa, 2020; Ddamulira et al., 2021; Geoffrey et al., 2014). In the Sudano-Sahelian zone of West Africa, tomato farmers face constraints such as poor soil fertility, extreme heat, and insufficient or unpredictable water supply, all of which have only become more precarious due to climate change (Perez et al., 2017). The authors further noted that biotic stresses create additional losses, with newly emerging plant diseases and pests causing decreased yields and serious reductions in produce quality. In general, these challenges can often be managed by the adoption of innovations along the value chain in tomato production. In recent years, significant efforts have been made to improve tomato cultivation worldwide, and key areas of focus include genetic improvement of tomato varieties with enhanced resistance to disease, pests, and environmental stress; the push towards adopting sustainable agricultural practices such as integrated pest management, precision agriculture, and soil health management; innovations in irrigation technology such as drip irrigation and soil moisture sensors in regions facing water scarcity; advances in fertilizer technology and practices; improved post-harvest innovations and logistics, including better storage and transportation (Gatahi, 2020). Similarly, in Africa, Perez et al. (2017) also noted that different efforts have been made by improving the varieties used in production, delivery of extension services and good agricultural practices, fostering market access, value chain development, and research and development.

Efforts to improve global tomato production have seen significant success in various areas along the value chain. For example, in Spain, advancements in breeding by INIA (Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria) include developing resistant lines through traditional and molecular breeding methods (Gil Molina, 2024). In the same vein, breeding efforts in Spain have succeeded in enhancing flavour profiles, texture, and shelf life to meet international market demands, using both traditional and biotechnological approaches (Alonso-Salinas et

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al., 2022). Innovations in cultivation techniques, pest management, and disease control have also played a role in tomato production (Khokhar & Kumar, 2024). For example, in Egypt, the adoption of greenhouses and plastic tunnels has helped in extending growing seasons, protecting plants from pests, and improving productivity under controlled conditions (Abdrabbo, Negm, Fath, & Javadi, 2019). While in Nigeria, innovations in post-harvest handling and processing, such as tomato paste production, have increased income and minimized wastage (Olayide, Obe, & Obisesan, 2024). In view of the foregoing, the study assesses the adoption of innovations along the tomato value chain in The Gambia with the aim of proffering solutions that can help increase the adoption and diffusion of these innovations, which could increase yield, income, and reduce losses.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Tomato cultivation is the second most prevalent vegetable production activity in The Gambia, after onions, and holds substantial potential to bolster food security and empower farmers, particularly women (Sanneh, Babana, & Yaffa, 2022). As highlighted by Ali et al. (2023), tomato farming not only serves as a critical nutritional source but also acts as a catalyst for economic independence.

Prioritizing the adoption of innovative agricultural practices within this sector is essential for addressing labour-intensive challenges, improving operational efficiency, and enhancing farmers' livelihoods. The African Union Commission (2022) underscores this perspective, emphasizing that innovation-driven growth in the tomato industry is vital for achieving food self-sufficiency and reducing dependence on imports, thereby conserving foreign currency reserves. Strategically investing in modern production techniques promises tangible benefits for both economic development and food security.

Despite its significance, tomato production in The Gambia contends with persistent infrastructural, climatic, and market-related challenges. Reliance on rain-fed agriculture renders yields vulnerable to erratic rainfall and prolonged dry seasons, often resulting in crop failure. Limited irrigation infrastructure, coupled with inadequate access to quality seeds, fertilizers, and pest control measures, further constrains productivity.

Although government initiatives such as the promotion of high-yielding, disease-resistant varieties, improved farming techniques, and enhanced market linkages have been introduced through agencies like the Department of Agriculture and the National Agriculture Research Institute, the extent of their adoption remains uncertain. This gap hampers efforts to fully leverage innovation for agricultural transformation. Consequently, there is a critical need to investigate the adoption levels of these innovations across the tomato value chain and assess their impact on production outcomes, informing targeted strategies for sustainable agricultural development in The Gambia.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The general objective of the study is to assess the adoption of innovations in the production of tomatoes in The Gambia. The specific objective of the study is to: Assess the benefits of adoption new technology on the production of tomatoes in The Gambia.

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between the adoption of innovations in the production of tomatoes and the yield of farmers.
2. There is no significant relationship between the adoption of innovations in the production of tomatoes and the income of farmers.
3. There is no significant relationship between the adoption of innovations in the production of tomatoes and the reduction of post-harvest losses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

The study used a survey research design and adopted the cross-sectional method. The research is both descriptive and qualitative in the study. This method is primarily concerned with describing and explaining the pattern of relationships between the adoption of innovations and tomato production in the study area. It also assisted the researcher in assessing a large sample of tomato farmers within a short time to draw inferences.

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Research Setting

The study was carried out in the Gambia. The Gambia is a small country in West Africa between latitudes 13°N and 14°N and longitudes 14°W and 17°W, occupying a total area of 11,420 sq. km. It stretches 450 km along the Gambia River, and the country (10,689 square kilometers) is surrounded by Senegal, except for a 60-km Atlantic Ocean front (Africa, 2013). The country has a population of 2.5 million. With 176 people per square kilometer, it is one of the most densely populated countries in Africa (Africa, 2013). The Gambia is organized into Local Government Areas (LGA), each of which either shares boundaries with a long-standing administrative unit known as a region or corresponds with roughly half of a region. The city of Banjul and the Kanifing Municipality each form a separate LGA. Most of the population (57%) is concentrated around urban and peri-urban centers (Arai, Knippenberg, Meyer & Witayangkurn, 2021). Most of the people live near the coast. Gambia's population is made up of several ethnic groups; about one-third are Mandinka, followed by Fula, Wolof, and Jola people. Spoken languages are English (official), Malinke, Fulani (Fulbe), Diola (Jola), and other indigenous languages and Creole. More than 95% of the population in the Islamic Republic of the Gambia is Muslim.

The study was carried out in the two agricultural regions of the Gambia, the West Coast Region and the North Bank Region, focusing on tomato farmers. The West Coast Region is one of the six subregions of the Gambia. The region is located in the western part of the country, west of the Atlantic Ocean, north of Banjul and Lower River Region, and Senegal is located in the south. The region itself is divided into nine districts. These districts are Foni Bintang-Karenai, Foni Bondali, Foni Brefet, Foni Jarrol, Foni Kansala, Kombo Central, East, and Kombo North/Saint Mary. The area is 1,764 square kilometers, and it has a population of 930,934 according to 2024 data (GBoS, 2024). Similarly, the North Bank region is located in the northern part of the country. The Atlantic is in the west, the Lower River region is in the south, and Senegal is in the north. The region itself is divided into six districts. These districts are Central Baddibu, Jokadu, Lower Baddibu, Lower Niuni, Upper Baddibu, and Upper Niuni. The area has a surface area of 2,256 square kilometers and has a population of 266,545 according to 2024 data (GBoS, 2024).

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Gambia

- Sample Villages
- 1 Farafenni
 - 2 Sukuta
 - 3 Kunkujang Mariama
 - 4 Banjul Nding
 - 5 Busumbala
 - 6 Basori
 - 7 Pirang
 - 8 Kampant
 - 9 Minteh Kunda
 - 10 Kerr Selleh
 - 11 Alkali Kunda
 - 12 Fass Njaga Choi
 - 13 Kerewan
 - 14 Kabba Koto
 - 15 Kabba

Figure 1: Map of the Study Area
Source: Gomez et al (2026)

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Population of the Study

The population for this study is made up of tomato farmers, both men and women, who were selected from the main tomato-producing districts. The Gambia Bureau of Statistics Integrated Household Survey (GBoS, 2020) report on agriculture revealed that there are 20,196 agricultural households engaged in tomato production in the two (2) regions selected in the study: the West Coast Region (14,196) and the North Bank Region (6,000). Out of the total agricultural households in the two regions, the HIS survey further highlighted that the following percentages represent the number of households cultivating tomatoes: Therefore, the population of tomato farmers in the study will be 20,196. The sample size of 396 was calculated using Yamane's (1973) formula.

Sampling Technique/Procedure

In establishing a sample size, a multistage sampling procedure was used; this included cluster sampling, purposive sampling, and simple random sampling. The primary sampling unit was the regions. Two agricultural regions (West Coast and North Bank) out of five (West Coast, Lower River, North Bank, Central River Region North, Central River Region South and Upper River Region) were purposely selected in the first stage of the research based on the high production of tomatoes and the delivered innovations in these regions, out of which two local government areas (each selected region has one LGA) were covered in the study.

The West Coast Region was clustered into nine districts (Foni Bintang-Karenai, Foni Bondali, Foni Brefet, Foni Jarrol, Foni Kansala, Kombo Central, Kombo East, Kombo North, and Kombo South), and out of the nine locations, four districts (Kombo South, Kombo North, East, and Foni Kansala) were randomly sampled. Then eight villages, two from each district, were randomly selected from Kombo East (Pirang and Basori) and Foni Kansala Kampant and Kappa, respectively. Kombo North (Sukuta, Busumbala, and Banjul Nding) has three villages because it is the largest district in the region, and Kombo South (Kunkujang Mariama) has one village because it is a smaller district.

In the same vein, the North Bank Region was also clustered into six districts, namely Central Baddibu, Jokadu, Lower Baddibu, Lower Niimi, Upper Baddibu, and Upper Niimi. Four districts were randomly selected: Upper Niimi, Upper Baddibu, Central Baddibu, and Lower Niimi, and then seven villages (Alkali Kunda, Farafenni, Kerewan, Kerr Selleh, Kabakoto, Fass Njaga Choi, and Minteh) were also randomly sampled. This gives a total of fifteen (15) tomato-cultivation villages (8 villages in the West Coast Region and 7 villages from the North Bank Region) that were used for the study.

Sample Size Determination

According to the Gambia Bureau of Statistics Integrated Household Survey (2020) agricultural report, there are 20,196. Tomato farmers in the two regions that were chosen. As a result, a margin error of 5% was included in the sample size formula for categorical data using the Taro Yamane (Yamane, 1973) method with a 95% confidence level. Applying the following formula:

$$n = N / (1 + N (e)^2)$$

Where:

n- Is the sample size

N- Known population and

e- Error level of precision or % per cent confidence interval or alpha level. For a 0.95 confidence interval, $e = 0.05$.

$$n = 20196 / (1 + 20196 (0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 20196 / (1 + 20196 (0.0025))$$

$$n = 20196 / (1 + 51)$$

$$n = 20196 / (51)$$

$$n = 396$$

Using the above mathematical formula, the minimum sample size is 396 based on the GBoS Integrated Housing Survey (2020). At the regional and village level, the breakdown of the respondents is shown in Table 2.

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Table 1: Number of Respondents from each Region

S/N	Administrative Region	Population	Percentage of Sample	Sample Size
1	West Coast Region	16,196	$16196/20196 \times 100 = 80\%$	80% of 396 = 317
2	North Bank Region	4000	$4000/20196 \times 100 = 20\%$	20% of 396 = 79
Total	2	20,196	100	396

Source: Gambia Bureau of Statistics (2020)

At the village level, the breakdown of the respondents is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by village

No	Administrative Region	Name of Local Government Area	District	Name of selected villages	Sample size per village	Total
1	West Coast Region	Brikama	Kombo South	Kunkujang	26	317
				Mariama		
			Kombo North	BanjulNding	42	
				Sukuta	54	
			Kombo East	Busumbala	39	
				Pirang	39	
				Basori	39	
			Foni Bondali	Kappa	39	
Foni Kansala	Kampant	39				
2	North Bank Region	Kerewan	Upper Nuimi	Farafenni	13	79
				Kerewan		
			Central Baddibu	Alkali Kunda	11	

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	Sabach Sanjal	Kerr Salleh	11
		Fass Njaga Choi	11
		Minteh Kunda	11
		Kabokoto	11
Total	2	2	396

Source: Field survey, 2023

3.6 Method of Data Collection

Four methods of data collection were adopted in this study for data collection. The methods include semi-structured questionnaires, focus group discussions (FGD), key informant interviews (KII) and Observation. These methods were used to triangulate to reduce biases. In the same vein, secondary data was obtained from journals, newspapers, books, conference papers, official documents, and reports from the Ministry of Agriculture, Department of Agriculture, National Agricultural Research Institute, and Food and Agriculture Organization. Research data was collected from May to August 2023 with the aid of three (4) research assistants and two (2) supervisors (Focus Group Discussion and Key Informant Interview) who were recruited and trained. The recruitment was done in line with the different languages spoken in these regions.

3.6.1 Structured Questionnaire

A structured questionnaire (Appendix II) was used in data collection from tomato farmers in the selected village gardens; these farmers were the primary respondents. This was appropriate in a descriptive study survey where the number of respondents is high. The questionnaire gathered information on different aspects of respondents' demographics and types of innovations, rate of adoption, facilitators of adoption, benefits of adoption, and challenges facing the adoption in tomato production. This was done with the help of field assistants, as a few of the farmers could not read or write. Farmers who couldn't read or write had the questionnaire read to them, and their answers were cross-checked with those on the questionnaire, and the right answers were ticked. When the right answers were not provided, the research assistant read out the options and ticked the one that the respondent chose.

3.6.2 Focus Group Discussion

Focus group discussions were conducted with selected tomato farmers to gain qualitative information about their views on the adoption of innovations in tomato production. The discussants were selected based on their years (at least 5 years) of cultivation of tomatoes and the amount of yield (20 kg and above). The reason is that they would have received training and innovations, and therefore can provide information on the adoption of innovations in the production of tomatoes.

Focus group discussions (FGDs) were held in each of the fifteen selected villages, with each group comprising minimum of six (6) discussants to maximum of ten (10) participants. This size facilitated easier coordination and management of the sessions. In each village, two FGDs were conducted: one for farmers aged 25 and younger and another for those aged 25 and older. This separation allowed participants to express their views freely, as younger individuals might feel shy or reserved when mixed with much older farmers. Moreover, this approach enabled the researcher to gather participants' opinions and observe their emotional responses and non-verbal cues more effectively. In total, thirty FGDs were conducted over four months, averaging two sessions per day.

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The FGD sessions were held in neutral settings with the participants sitting around a table or chairs arranged in a circle to better facilitate conversation. The researcher moderated all the sessions of the discussions in the local languages, and audio recorders were used to provide an accurate transcript of a session, with one research assistant serving as a note-taker to document the sessions. Another research assistant served as an observer. The moderator asked open-ended questions and also encouraged group interactions, which revealed important insights regarding discussion outcomes. At the end of each FGD session, a debriefing was done to gain the opinion of observers' perspectives, which was utilized during analysis.

3.6.3 Key Informant Interview

Apart from triangulating the data collected from the structured questionnaire and FGDs, key informant interviews were valuable in providing opinions, experiences, values, and various aspects of the population regarding the adoption of innovations in the production of tomatoes in the Gambia. Key informant interviews were conducted with people who have first-hand information on tomato production in the Gambia. An interview guide comprising open-ended questions was developed to keep the researcher in line with the research objectives. This method was used because it helped uncover vital data on the research objectives and augment the information supplied by respondents from the questionnaire and FGDs.

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select the informants to be interviewed because they have experience and knowledge of tomato production. The following key informants were selected for the interviews: village extension workers, regional agricultural directors, and the National Agricultural Research Institute (NARI) to gain their opinions on the adoption of innovations in tomato production.

A total of nine (9) key informants were interviewed in the two local government areas, and they include six (6) extension workers, one from each district, two (2) staff of NARI, and the Deputy Director of Horticulture Services. The key informants were interviewed individually at their convenience for three weeks. A tape recorder/handset was used to record the interview sessions, while the researcher jotted down the important points. Each interview schedule was less than one hour.

3.6.4 Observation

The researcher also utilized unstructured observation as it allowed the researcher to capture spontaneous behaviors. The researcher observed the available innovations in tomato production in each village garden. Observation can also provide insights into the context and dynamics of social interactions that other methods, like surveys or interviews, might miss, and it allows researchers to gather data as events happen, capturing behaviors in their natural settings without relying on participants' recollections or interpretations.

3.7 Techniques of Data Analysis

3.7.1 Quantitative analysis

The analyses were broadly divided into two sections, A and B. The first part of the survey has to do with the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents, and the second part is the research objectives. These were presented in tables using statistics such as frequencies, simple percentages, mean, standard deviation figures, Pearson correlation, t-test, regression analysis, and chi-square-based statistics. All these were done with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, 26.0). A descriptive analysis of what is presented in the tables gave a clearer picture of what the figures in the table stand for. The hypotheses were tested using the chi-square analytical tool to ascertain the level of relationship between the variables as stated in the hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. The formula for chi-square, as given by Emaikwu (2015), is hereby stated as follows:

$$X^2 = \frac{\sum (O - E)^2}{E}$$

Where:

X² stands for Chi-square

Σ stands for the summation of

O stands for observed frequencies and

E stands for the expected outcome.

The qualitative data obtained from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions would be transcribed, typed, and categorized, and a content analysis made of them.

3.7.2 Qualitative analysis

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The data collected was transcribed for all the focus groups and key informant interview comments. Data were sorted and categorized and a content analysis was made of them. The comments were rearranged to have answers grouped for each discussion and interview protocol based on the research objectives. The main ideas were organized into themes to generate an idea or ideas, and quotations were identified for each theme. The findings were written in a narrative to describe the themes with quotations. This analysis allowed the exploration of relationships between the variables studied.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

This section highlights the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. The variables analyzed include sex, age, education, and farming experience. Hence, the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents in the study are presented below.

Table 3: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Variable	Frequency N = 396	Percentage % = 100
Sex		
Male	15	3.8
Female	381	96.2
Age		
Less than 20 years	2	0.5
20-29 years	24	6.1
30-39 years	107	27
40-49 years	146	36.9
50 years and above	117	29.5
Education		
Non-literate	297	75
Primary	52	13.1
Secondary education	22	5.6
Senior secondary education	17	4.3
Tertiary	8	2.0
Years of Tomato Cultivation		
5-10 years	77	19.4
11-15 years	143	36.1
16 years and above	176	44.4
Belong to a Farmer Field School		
Yes	240	60.6
No	156	39.4
Access to Credit		
Yes	74	18.7
No	322	81.3

Source: Field Survey, 2023

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Table 3 shows a summary of the socio-demographic data of respondents. Regarding the distribution of respondents' gender, 3.8% (n=15) of the respondents were male, and 381 (96.2%) respondents were female. This finding is consistent with that of the West Africa Competitiveness Project [WACOMP] (2023), which reported that 95% of tomato producers in the Gambia are women, while 5% are male. Similarly, a study conducted by Sanneh, Babana, & Yaffa (2022) in the Gambia revealed that 70% of tomato farmers were female and 30% were male.

The data obtained in the table above also revealed the age of respondents. The data indicates that 2 (.5%) respondents were less than 20 years, 6.1% (n=24) were between the ages of 20-29 years, while 27% (n=107) were between 30-39 years, 36.9% (n=146) were between 40-49 years, and 29.5% (n=117) were 50 years and above. The majority of the respondents are 40 years and above. The data collected and analyzed in the table above also shows that the majority, 66.4% respondents, were above 40 years old. This finding also implies that extension agents and project staff who work with tomato farmers should concentrate their work on all age categories of farmers.

The educational qualification distribution of the respondents established that out of 396 participants, 75% (n=297) had no formal education, while 13.1% (n=52) had primary education, 5.65% (n=22) had secondary education, 4.3% (n=17) had senior secondary education, and 8 (2%) had tertiary education. This result shows that the majority (75%) of respondents do not have formal education, which could impact the adoption of innovations in tomato production.

The results in Table 3 also revealed that 19.4 % (n=77) of respondents have been in tomato production for about 5-10 years, while those with 11-15 years were 36.2% (n=143), and 44.4% (n=176) had above 15 years of experience in cultivating tomatoes. This result indicates that the majority of the respondents had 10 years and above of experience. Data on respondents who attend a farmer field school is also displayed in the table. According to the data, 60.6% (n=240) of respondents agreed with the statement that they belonged to an FFS, whereas 39.4% (n=156) disagreed. According to the analysis, few farmers had access to credit, 18.7% (n=74), and the rest of the farmers, 81.3% (n=322), had no access to credit. This shows that credit was not available to the majority of respondents. This finding is consistent with the economic constraint paradigm of adoption (Sitomwe et al., 2016). This is also consistent with Ateka, Mbeche & Muendo (2021), Burke et al. (2019), and Melkani et al. (2019), who argue that in the presence of liquidity constraints, asset-poor households may be dissuaded from entering into high-value agricultural activities due to a lack of enough capital (and they did not have access to credit) or capacity to cope with market risks.

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This section highlights the benefits derived from adopting innovations in the production of tomatoes. The opinions of farmers on the benefits derived from adopting the available innovations in tomato production in the study area include higher yields, income, and postharvest losses.

Yield

Adopting the available innovations in the study area is said to have increased yield. The findings are displayed in the table below.

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Table 4: Yield of tomatoes before and after the adoption of the innovations

Increase in Yield Tomatoes	Frequency of N=396	Percentage % = 100	Yield before adoption/ non-adoption	Frequency N=396	Percentage %=100	Yield after adoption/ non-adoption	Frequency N=396	Percentage %=100	% change	Sig.
Agree	299	75.5	<50kg	252	63.6	<50kg	65	16.4	47.2	.000
Disagree	97	24.5	50-99kg	129	32.6	50-99kg	145	36.6	4	
			100-149kg	15	3.8	100-149kg	113	28.5	24.7	
						>150kg	73	18.5	18.5	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The data collected and analysed show that 75.5% (n=299) of respondents agree that they have realized an increase in their yield after adopting the new technology/innovations, while 24.5% (n=97) disagree. The finding shows that the majority of the respondents had an increase in their yield. This also implies that the adoption of innovations affects the yield of farmers in the study area. Further analysis also showed similar results. The results from the yield of farmers before and after the adoption of the innovations are shown in Table 16. The data therefore show that farmers who had a yield of less than 50 kg before the adoption of the available innovations/innovations were 63.3% (n=252), 32.6% (n=129) respondents had a yield between 50-99 kg, while 3.8% (n=15) had between 100-149 kg. The table also shows the data for the yield after the adoption of the innovations: 16.45 (n=65) respondents had a yield of less than 50 kg, 36.6% (n=145) had a yield between 50 and 99 kg, 28.5% (n=113) had a yield between 100 and 149 kg, and 18.5% (n=73) respondents had a yield above 150 kg. The table also shows the difference in yield percentage, which is presented as a 47.2% change in yield (less than 50 kg) than before adoption and after adoption of the available innovations; a 4% change was also noticed in 50-99 kg; a 24.7% change in the yield 100-149 kg; while an 18.5% was for farmers who had above 150 kg and above. A one-way ANOVA was also conducted to identify the significance of the changes in yield before and after adoption, and the *P-value* was given as 0.000. The finding shows a significant positive change in the yield of tomatoes after the farmers adopt the innovations.

Similar findings were also found during the FGD sessions, which highlighted that the majority of the discussants noted that since they have access to the innovations/innovations their yields have increased tremendously. The fruit yield data obtained during the FGD sessions indicate that farmers have increased in yield after adopting the innovations. It was also observed that those who utilized the available innovations had higher yields than those who did not. The yield ranges from 15 to 30 pans or baskets, depending on the region and its unit of measurement, for those that adopted the innovations, while non-adopters have a yield range of 5 to 10 pans or baskets. This was stated by a discussant from Farafenni Village Garden in the North Bank Region of the Gambia:

Our garden is not sponsored, so we do not benefit like other village gardens, ... Our tomato yield is almost the same every year. The season before last, I had just 3 pans of tomatoes after harvesting and last year, I had 2 ½ pans (Source: FGD, 17th May 2023).

Similar comments were made in Alkali Kunda Village Garden:

Our tomato yield is almost the same as that of last year. I had 6 pans of Mongal last year and the same amount this season, too. As you can see, our garden is not fenced, with no borehole and other interventions like other gardens (Source: FGD, 18th May 2023).

In contrast, other village gardens that have average or above average adoption of the available innovations in the study area have increased their tomato yield. According to a 45-year-old discussant from Sukuta Village Garden:

“During the Chinese time, we strictly utilised all the available innovations in the garden, especially the improved varieties and compost making, and we had a bumper harvest. We harvest our tomatoes for three months continuously” (Source: FGD, 30th May 2023).

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II. Income

Tomato production is said to be beneficial in the study area because it not only serves as a source of employment for many women, but it also provides income for them and their families. The findings are shown in the table below.

Table 5: Income of tomato farmers before and after the adoption of the innovation

Increase in Income	Frequency N=396	Percentage % = 100	Income before adoption/non-adoption (GMD)	Frequency N=396	Percentage % =100	Income after adoption/non-adoption (GMD)	Frequency N=396	Percentage % =100	% change	Sig.
Agree	288	72.7	<5,000	162	40.9	<5000	32	8.1	32.8	.003
Disagree	108	27.3	5001-10,000	228	57.6	5000-10,000	117	29.5	28.1	
			10,001-15,000	6	1.5	10,001-15,000	156	39.4	37.9	
						15,001-20,000	65	16.4	16.4	
						>20,000	26	6.6	6.6	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The data collected and analyzed show that 72.7% (n=288) respondents agree that they have realized an increase in their income after adopting the new technology/innovations, while 27.3% (n=108) disagree. The finding shows that the majority of the respondents had an increase in their income. This also implies that the adoption of innovations affects the income of farmers in the study area. Further analysis also showed similar results. The results from the analysis of the income before adoption and after the adoption of the innovations also shows that farmers who had an income of less than D5000 before the adoption of the available innovations/innovations were 40.9% (n=162), 57.6% (n=228) of respondents had an income between D5001-10,000, while 1.5% (n=6) had between D10,001-15,000. The data also shows the data for income after the adoption of the innovations; 8.1% (n=32) respondents had an income of less than D5,000; similarly, 29.5% (n=117) had an income of between D5000-10,000; 39.4% (n=156) had an income between D10,001-15,000; 16.4% (n=65) had an income between 15,001-20,000; and 6.6% (n=26) had an income above D20,000. The table also shows the change in income percentage before and after the adoption of innovations, which is presented as a 32.8% change in the income of farmers who earned less than D5000 before adoption and after adoption of the available innovations; a 28.1% change was also noticed in respondents who had an income between D5000-10,000; similarly, a 37.9% change was also found among respondents who had an income between D10,001-15,000; 16.4% among respondents with an income between 15,001-20,000; and respondents with an income above D20,000 had 6.6%. Further analyses using one-way ANOVA were also conducted to identify the significance of the changes in yield before and after adoption, and the *P-value* was given as 003. The finding shows a positive, significant change in the income of the respondents who adopted the innovations.

In the same vein, similar findings were also found in the FGD and KII sessions. According to a discussant during an FGD session in Kunkujang Mariama Village Garden:

We benefit a lot from the tomatoes production in the Garden. I made more than D10,000 (\$150) from the sale of tomatoes alone, which I use to settle or pay the school bills of my children (Source: FGD, 12th October, 2023).

In parallel, a discussant from Alkali Kunda in the North Bank Region highlighted that:

We have a lot of benefits from the garden, the income gained is spent on the family's upkeep, such as payment of school fees, buying uniforms for the kids and giving them money for school lunches. We also buy soap as well as contributions for 'Osusu'. We also buy rice from the proceeds of the garden and add to the fish money for the household. We use some of the tomatoes for cooking at home as well. By doing so, it reduces what we spend in the market (Source: FGD, 18th May 2023).

The above findings are consistent with the comments from the FDG in BanjulNding Site II:

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The women gain a lot of income from the sales of the tomatoes, some make as much as D20,000 (\$270) to D30,000 (\$445) per season. They pay the school fees of their children and solve their expenses and those of their children especially those that are widowed. Some of them have bought land to build their compounds from the proceeds they gain from this garden (Source: FGD, 10th October 2023).

In the same vein, a KII with the Principal HTS officer pointed out that:

The benefits the women gain from these tomato schemes especially tomatoes, are numerous. They mostly sell the produce at the end of the season, which generates them income. Many use it for paying school fees for their children. Some of them are breadwinners, especially the ones who are widows solely take the responsibility of taking care of their families. Some of them use the proceeds to help their family members, especially their parents, in old age (Source: KII, 3rd June, 2023).

The findings of the study relating to the benefits derived from tomato production found that women gain a lot of benefits through the sales of their produce, which generates the needed income to pay household bills such as school fees for their children, contributing to helping their spouses financially in the family upkeep and financial independence. This implies that tomato production has significantly improved the lives and livelihoods of the women involved, which trickles down to their families and society at large. Moreover, their venture has helped improve the nutrition of their households with regular intake of tomatoes, which is important in our daily diets, and has improved the health of many households in their communities. The findings above are in line with the views of Asadu et al. (2018). Tomato production has also helped women meet their life-sustaining ventures as well as improve the nutritional status of their households. In the same vein, tomato production benefits people even beyond the producers; all people involved in other segments of the value chain benefit from it directly and indirectly, thereby curbing the high poverty rate among rural dwellers (Mukaila et al., 2022).

III. Postharvest losses

The data collected was also analysed for the post-harvest benefits farmers derive from adopting the available innovations/innovations. The data analysed is presented in the table below.

Table 6: Postharvest losses of tomatoes before and after the adoption of the innovation

Adoption of Innovations	Frequency to N=396	Percentage % = 100	Level of PHL before adoption/no n-adoption	Frequency N=396	Percentage %=100	Level of PHL after adoption/no n-adoption	Frequency N=396	Percentage %=100	% change	Sig.	
Reduce Postharvest Losses	Agree	123	31.1	10-15kg	17	4.3	<10kg	84	21.2	16.9	0.143
	Disagree	273	68.9	16-20kg	78	19.7	10-15kg	51	12.9	6.8	
				21-25kg	109	27.5	16-20kg	63	15.9	11.6	
				Above 25kg	192	48.5	20-25kg	84	21.2	27.3	
						>25kg	114	28.8	28.8		

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The data collected and analyzed shows that 31.1% (n=123) respondents agree that they have realized a reduction in postharvest losses of their tomatoes after adopting the new technology/innovations, while 68.9% (n=273) disagree. The finding shows that the majority of the respondents do not have a reduction in their tomato postharvest losses. This implies that the

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adoption of innovations does not affect the level of postharvest losses in the study area. Further analysis also showed similar results. The results from the analysis of the income before adoption and after the adoption of the innovations are shown in Table 20. The data shown in the table above shows that farmers had postharvest losses of between 10-15 kg before the adoption of the available innovations/innovations: 4.3% (n=17), 19.7% (n=78) respondents had losses between 16-20 kg, while 27.5% (n=109) had between 21-25 kg of losses. The data also shows that after the adoption of the innovations, 21.2% (n=84) respondents had postharvest losses of less than 10 kg; similarly, 12.9% (n=51) had postharvest losses of between 16-20 kg, while 21.2% (n=84) had postharvest losses of 20-25 kg, while 28.8% (n=114) had postharvest losses of above 25 kg. The table also shows the change in postharvest percentage before and after the adoption of innovations, which is presented as a 16.9% change in the postharvest losses of farmers who had losses of less than 10 kg before adoption, and after the adoption of the available innovations, a 6.8% change was also noticed in respondents who had losses between 10-15 kg; similarly, an 11.6% change was also found among respondents who had losses between 16-20 kg, and 27.3% among respondents with losses between 20-25 kg, and respondents with losses above 25 kg had 28.8%. Further analyses using one-way ANOVA were also conducted to identify the significance of the changes in postharvest losses before and after adoption, and the *P-value* was found to be .143. The finding shows a significant negative change in the postharvest losses of the respondents who adopted the innovations.

This implies that the adoption of innovations didn't reduce the level of postharvest losses in the study area. Furthermore, this could be a result of the non-adoption of new processing technologies/innovations or the non-availability of storage technologies/innovations for farmers in the study area. The increase in postharvest losses could also be due to the increase in the yield of farmers who adopted the postharvest losses. This finding is similar to that of Tobe, Atala, Saddiq, and Damisa (2023), who found that the awareness and adoption of improved tomato post-harvest management practices were not sufficient to improve the outcome of farmers in terms of loss reduction and income.

Evaluation of Hypothesis

This section is concerned with the evaluation of the hypothesis formulated for the study. Three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Chi-square was used to analyze the data.

Ho¹: *There is no association between the adoption of innovations in tomato production and the yield of farmers.*

Table 7: Chi-Square Table

Chi-Square Tests				
		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square		188.941 ^a	9	.000
Likelihood Ratio		256.015	9	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association		138.930	1	.000
N of Valid Cases		396		
Symmetric Measures				
		Value	Approximate Significance	
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.691	.000	
	Cramer's V	.691	.000	
N of Valid Cases		396		

A chi-square (χ^2) test was conducted to assess the association between farmers' adoption of the innovation and the categorization of tomato yield. The results demonstrated a statistically significant relationship between the variables. The Pearson chi-square statistic was 188.941 with 9 degrees of freedom, and this value exceeds the critical chi-square value for $df = 9$ at the conventional significance level ($p < .001$). For reference, at $\alpha = 0.05$, the critical value for chi-square with 9 degrees of freedom is approximately 16.92. Since the observed value (188.941) is substantially higher than this cutoff, the result is highly significant, indicating a strong association between the variables.

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Additional tests support this conclusion. The likelihood ratio chi-square is even higher at 256.015, compared to the same degrees of freedom, also indicating significance ($p < .001$). The linear-by-linear association test yielded a value of 138.930, further confirming a significant linear trend in the data ($p < .001$). The measures of association, Phi and Cramér's V, both indicate a strong relationship, with a value of 0.691 and significance of $p < .001$, suggesting a large effect size.

This finding implies that adoption of the innovation is positively associated with tomato yields among farmers in the sample. Therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis, which states that there is no association between the adoption of innovations in tomato production and the yield of farmers.

Ho²: *There is no association between the adoption of innovations in tomato production and the income level of farmers.*

The above hypothesis seeks to ascertain the association between the adoption of innovations and the income of tomato farmers in the study area. The study used chi-square to evaluate the assumption as indicated in Table 19 below.

Table 8: Chi-Square Summary Table

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	185.477 ^a	3	.000
Likelihood Ratio	234.496	3	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	129.420	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	396		

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.684	.000
	Cramer's V	.684	.000
N of Valid Cases		396	

A chi-square test of independence was conducted to examine the association between the categorical variables. The test revealed a statistically significant relationship, $\chi^2(11, N = 396) = 185.477$, $p < .001$. The effect size, as measured by Cramer's V, was large, $V = .684$, indicating a strong association between the variables. These findings also imply that adoption of the innovation is positively associated with higher income among farmers in the sample. Further analysis also shows that the calculated value is higher than the critical value; therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis that states that there is no association between the adoption of innovations in tomato production and the yield of farmers.

Ho³: *The adoption of innovations and the level of postharvest losses of tomatoes are independent (no association).*

The above hypothesis seeks to ascertain the association between the adoption of innovations and the level of postharvest losses of tomatoes in the study area. The study used chi-square to evaluate the assumption, as indicated in Table 20 below.

Table 9: Chi-Square Table

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	153.076 ^a	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	211.788	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	152.421	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	396		

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0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 34.66.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.622	.000
	Cramer's V	.622	.000
N of Valid Cases		396	

A chi-square test was conducted to examine the association between the variables in the study. The results of the Pearson Chi-Square test indicated a significant association, $\chi^2(2, N = 396) = 153.08, p < .001$, suggesting that the variables are not independent of each other. The likelihood ratio test corroborated these findings, $\chi^2(2, N = 396) = 211.79, p < .001$, further supporting the conclusion that there is a statistically significant relationship between the variables.

Additionally, the Linear-by-Linear Association test revealed a significant linear relationship, $\chi^2(1, N = 396) = 152.42, p < .001$. The expected counts for all cells exceeded the minimum threshold (the smallest expected count was 34.66), indicating that the chi-square test's assumptions were met. Symmetric measures of association demonstrated a strong relationship between the variables, with Phi and Cramér's V both equal to .622, $p < .001$. These large effect size indicators suggest a substantial association between the variables.

In summary, the analyses reveal a significant and strong association between the variables under investigation, as indicated by the chi-square tests and the measures of effect size. These findings suggest that the variables are related in a meaningful way within this sample. Therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis that states that there is no association between the adoption of innovations in tomato production and the yield of farmers.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results, the study concluded that tomato production is mostly carried out by female farmers in The Gambia, the majority of whom are 40 years of age and older. The study also ascertained that the available innovations in tomato production include nursery and garden bed preparation, improved and hybrid tomato varieties, spacing of tomatoes during planting, staking, compost making and application, pest control, training on harvesting indices and techniques, and processing of tomatoes into various products.

The study also concluded that the majority of the farmers have adopted most of the available innovations in tomato production; the rate of adoption of innovations is also high. In the same vein, the adoption rate for greenhouses and processing innovations was equally low.

The study concluded that tomato farmers have derived benefits from the adopted innovations in the production of tomatoes in The Gambia, which include the change in yield and income of farmers, while postharvest losses of tomatoes were on the increase.

Based on the findings and conclusions reached, the following recommendations were made:

1. There is a need for the Department of Agriculture to strengthen farmer-to-farmer information pathways by training a few farmers (contact farmers) on the existing agricultural innovations so that they can disseminate the same to their colleagues in the study area. This will facilitate more contact with farmers and, in turn, promote the spread of the benefits of adopting agricultural innovation in tomato production.
2. Timely provision of improved or hybrid seeds to farmers: The Department of Agriculture, agricultural projects, and other stakeholders that provide seeds should do so before August; this will give farmers ample time to prepare their nurseries.
3. Provision of Loans and Grants to Farmers: There should be deliberate efforts toward assisting farmers with finance that will help them acquire modern processing and storage facilities that will help them process and store tomatoes into other food forms, which extends their shelf life. To the end, the government, through the Central Bank of The Gambia and other financial institutions, should intensify efforts in providing farmers with grants and soft loans with a lower interest rate that will enable them to meet the demands of modern post-harvest handling of crops, especially tomatoes.

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4. Provision of durable drip irrigation lines: Projects engaged in providing irrigation systems to farmers should procure durable irrigation lines that can serve farmers for a longer period, and the drip irrigation installment should be properly done to allow farmers to have access to water in all parts of the garden; this will reduce the water shortage challenges found in the study. To increase the adoption rate of innovations in tomato production, farmers should provide support and encouragement to each other so that they can master the innovation skills within a short period. Farmers are influenced by their social network in adopting or considering an innovation. Since many farmers do not want to be left behind, they will adopt the available innovations to boost production.
5. Farmers need to utilize the skills, knowledge, and innovations provided to them; this would increase their yield and income and reduce postharvest losses.

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